

A STUDY ON OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG BANK EMPLOYEES

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ABSTRACT:

A stress is a universal reality that all individuals acknowledge regardless of their employment. This study investigates the occupational stress of public and private employees who work for banks. Stress on the workplace may be a struggle for banking personnel all over the world; stress can be both beneficial and detrimental. There is already a certain amount of stress in banking workers' work lives, and they are then subjected to additional stress as a result of the work pressure that Banking employees confront on the job. The purpose of this study is to look at the elements that impact bank employee turnover, such as work environment, stress, and job satisfaction. According to a various studies related to employees from private and public banks, occupational stress is higher among private bank employees than among public bank employees. When faced with job diversity, discrimination, favoritism, delegating, and competing responsibilities, bank personnel cannot afford to relax and "wind down."

Keywords: OCCUPATIONAL STRESS, PUBLIC BANK EMPLOYEES, PRIVATE BANK EMPLOYEES, JOB SATISFACTION, WORK PRESSURE.

INTRODUCTION:

Stress is defined as the body's non-specific response to demands placed on it. When a person cannot cope with the challenges he or she encounters, stress is the outcome of a mismatch between him and his environment. When an individual's physical and emotional abilities do not match the demands of their job, stress results.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- Workplace stress levels among public and private bank employees.
- Developing knowledge of various research perspectives on stress management and employee performance.
- To study the methods used in the banking industries to lessen workplace stress.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A review of the literature to gain an understanding of the areas of research that has already been conducted on potential areas that have yet to be covered. In this way, an attempt has been made

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to provide a brief overview of previous contributions to the field of stress management and employee performance in the banking sector.

Mr. Manjunatha M K, Dr. T P Renukamurthy (2017) Banking personnel already undergo a certain amount of stress at work, and they then experience additional stress as a result of the workload pressure they are subjected to. Many workers find it difficult to adapt to the professions' frequent changes. Role conflict, customer service, contribution, rapid technological change, and a lack of responsiveness from customers are the top sources of stress for banking employees.

Mrs. Caral Lopes, Ms. Dhara Kachalia, (2016), They carried out study in both public and private banks. They showed how the banking industry has been transformed by technology and how the current state of the economy has made competitiveness more worldwide. Stress levels are rising for banking industry workers as well. Bank personnel should develop unique coping mechanisms for preserving their health and wellbeing in order to improve quality.

Priyanka Das, Alok Kumar Srivastav (2015), They have observed that managing employees at work is necessary for improving occupational health and safety. Organizational income will rise and staff retention will improve if employers take better care of their workers' psychological wellbeing. Since "a healthy employee is a productive employee," as the saying goes. They came to the conclusion that the selected public sector banks are only moderately stressed.

WHEN AFFECTED BY WORK STRESS PEOPLE MAY:

1. Become more and more anxious and worried.
2. Lose the ability to disengage or focus.
3. Find it challenging to reason and make decisions.
4. They feel less dedicated to and like their work less.
5. Experience fatigue, depression, and anxiety.
6. Have trouble falling asleep.
7. Have severe bodily issues including heart disease, high blood pressure, or headaches.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research used secondary data. In this way, many online journals were examined and taken into consideration for the study.

FINDINGS:

1. Work/role overload and a "high effort-reward imbalance" are two key drivers of stress for bank personnel.
2. Stress is inversely proportional to experience, i.e. the greater the experience, the lesser the stress.
3. Employee roles and duties play a major role in stress.
4. Female employees are more stressed.
5. Job dissatisfaction is caused by job stress.
6. Job Employee performance is negatively affected by stress.
7. Employees of private banks are more stressed by banking sector modernization than employees of state banks.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. Training in stress management
2. Stress management solutions –
 - Workload; the process of role reduction and modification.
 - Promote open communication to reduce stress from the workplace.

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- Conduct a stress assessment.
- To manage occupational strategy, introduce "Pranayama" (brain stilling and regulation of vital force) as a comprehensive management plan.
- Reward hard work and reward smart work.
- Offer people and work-related counselling, as well as assistance from a group of welfare, health, and counselling staff.

CONCLUSION:

It has substantial influences on how employees behave and change both on and off the job. Employees' general health has an impact on their performance. Stress management techniques like meditation and positive thinking are effective. It enhances the psychological and physical wellness of the workers.

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